

Impact of Recommendation Algorithms on Media Configuration

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of recommendation algorithms in media configuration. The rationale for this study stems from the growing importance of recommendation algorithms in media configuration. This study was anchored on the filter bubble theory by Eli Pariser (2011), which explains how personalised recommendation systems influence the type of information users receive, potentially limiting their exposure to diverse viewpoints. The researchers used a survey research design and collected data through questionnaire, with the target population of 1,304,998 for residents of Egor, Oredo and Ikpoba Okha and the sample size of 400, as determined by the Taro Yamane formula, with an error margin of 0.05. The findings showed that there is a high level of exposure and engagement with media content recommended by algorithms. Also, there is skepticism about the effectiveness of these algorithms, but this is not so with the business sector as recommendation systems benefit businesses by improving advertising and marketing strategies. The researchers, therefore, recommend that users should be educated to help them understand how algorithms shape their media consumption and empower them to make informed choices. Platforms should implement measures to prevent filter bubbles and echo chambers.

Keywords: Recommendation, Algorithm, Media, Configuration, Recommendation Algorithm, Media Configuration